

Questionnaire on Vertical Farming in Residential Building Balconies

Vertical farming is exactly what it sounds like: farming **on vertical surfaces (stacked layers)** rather than traditional, horizontal agriculture. It often incorporates **controlled-environment agriculture**, which aims to optimize plant growth, and soilless farming techniques. By using vertically stacked layers, much more food can be produced on the same amount of land (or even less).

This questionnaire aims to gather **insights from residents** regarding their awareness, acceptance, and perception of the idea of integrating vertical farming systems into their residential building balconies. Your responses will help understand the potential benefits, concerns, and feasibility of implementing such systems in residential building balconies.

A. Demographic Data:

1. Age:
2. Gender:
 - Male.
 - Female.

B. General Acceptance/benefits of the Idea:

3. Have you heard before about vertical farming?
 - Yes.
 - No.
4. Would you be open/interested in the idea of having a vertical farming system on your residential balcony?
 - Yes.
 - No.
 - Yes, if only affordable.
5. In your opinion, what is the primary benefit of integrating vertical farming into residential balconies? **Pick all that applies.**
 - Aesthetics and greenery benefits.
 - Economic benefits (e.g. fresh food production, food selling, ...etc.).
 - Environmental benefits.
 - Health and personal well-being benefits (e.g. relaxation).
 - Other (please specify).
6. What type of plants would you prefer to grow in a vertical farming system?
 - Edible crops (vegetables, herbs, fruits).
 - Ornamental plants and flowers.
 - Medicinal or aromatic plants.
 - A mix of all of the above.

C. Economic Benefits:

7. Would you consider growing your food on your balconies as a viable economic solution to reduce the cost of buying food, such as vegetables and fruits?
 - Yes.
 - No.

D. Health and Well-being:

8. Do you think growing your own fresh vegetables and herbs on your balcony would improve your overall health and nutrition versus reliance on store-bought, potentially less healthy options?
 - Yes.
 - No.
9. Do you believe that vertical farming at home can contribute to greater organic food security for residents?
 - Yes.
 - No.

E. Visual Appeal

10. Do you believe that vertical farming would enhance the visual aesthetics of your balcony?
 - Yes.
 - No.

F. Challenges and Concerns:

11. What concerns you the most when integrating a vertical farming system on your balconies? **Pick all that applies.**
 - Periodical watering and irrigation.
 - Time and effort required for care.
 - Cost of setup and maintenance.
 - Pests control and hygiene.
 - Humidity.
 - Cleaning issues (Soil spillage).
 - Pruning & Plants debris.
 - Other (please specify).
12. If vertical farming were a communal feature in your building, how would you prefer it to be managed? **Pick all that applies.**
 - Managed by residents collectively.
 - Maintained by a hired professional/gardener.
 - Automated system with minimal human involvement.
 - I wouldn't be interested in a communal system.

G. Proposed Vertical Farming Alternatives Assessment:

13. In your opinion, which of the following options would provide the greatest sense of comfort and ease in handling and maintaining the plants?
 - Option 1
 - Option 2
 - Option 3
14. From your perspective, which option offers a better natural view and fosters a stronger connection with nature?
 - Option 1
 - Option 2
 - Option 3

15. In your opinion, which of the options would least interfere with other uses of the balcony or window space, such as drying clothes, for example?
- Option 1
 - Option 2
 - Option 3
16. Which of the three options do you believe provides the best balance between functionality (planting) and aesthetic appearance?
- Option 1
 - Option 2
 - Option 3
17. Considering all the aspects addressed in the previous questions, which option would you prefer if vertical planting were to be integrated into your balcony?
- Option 1
 - Option 2
 - Option 3
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Thank you for taking the time to share your thoughts! Your responses will help us better understand community attitudes towards vertical farming and its potential benefits.